

HIGH-PRECISION HYBRID COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR SPACE OPTICS

T. Yokoyama^{1*}, T. Zama¹, S. Uehara¹, S. Sakane¹, T. Ozaki²

¹Super Resin Inc., Tokyo, Japan, ²Composites R & D, Tokyo, Japan

* Corresponding author (t_yokoyama@super-resin.co.jp)

Keywords: *CFRP, Ceramics, Space Optics, High-Precision*

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are positively applied to the structures and the components of space satellites such as bus structures, antenna reflectors and solar array panels both to reduce weight and to keep dimensional stability in orbit. In space optics requiring much higher precision, however, the application of CFRP is limited.

One of the major factors to restrain the application of CFRP to space optics is deformation of CFRP parts due to the moisture absorption of the matrix resin. By using cyanate ester resin having less moisture absorption than conventional epoxy resin, some structural parts such as metering tubes have been put to the practical use¹⁾. In addition, several optical mirrors were also demonstrated at laboratory level²⁾⁻⁴⁾.

Another factor is the difficulty of precise machining of the composite optical parts at sub-micron level due to the difference in the hardness of the fibers and the resin matrix.

The precision of the optics depends not only on the mirrors and supporting structures but also the fittings and interfaces to assemble the optical system. In order to realize such precise machining, structural materials should be suitable for drilling, grinding and polishing.

The authors have been developing a new hybrid composite structure in which CFRP parts and machinable ceramic parts are combined. The CFRP parts are mainly used to support load in the structure and the ceramic parts are used to make smooth surface for the mirrors and the

precise interfaces. In this paper, a demonstrator was fabricated and examined to verify the basic concept.

2 Fabrication of the demonstrator

2.1 The first demonstrator

The CFRP material and the ceramic material were selected to comply the requirement of low thermal deformation, low moisture deformation, low outgassing, and good machinability for precise machining.

2.1.1 CFRP material

High modulus carbon fibers were selected to have high thermal stability. Cyanate ester resin with low moisture absorption was selected to control hygroscopic deformation. Isotropic laminates of $[0^\circ/90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ/90^\circ]$ s were fabricated using an autoclave.

The outgassing of the laminates was evaluated first using GC-MS (Shimadzu), and no siloxane gas was detected.

The density and the Young's modulus of the CFRP were shown in Fig.1.

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was also evaluated using laser displacement sensors. Quasi-isotropic CFRP tubes whose length was 500 mm were fabricated by sheet winding. A pair of small mirrors was attached to the both ends of the tube. The change in the length was monitored by a set of the laser displacement sensor when the tube was heated from 25 degree C up to 115 degree C.

Figure 2 shows the result. The average value of CTE of the CFRP laminates was -0.34 ppm/K.

Table 1 Properties of the CFRP

Material Properties		
Density	g/cm ³	1.64
Young Modulus	GPa	112

Fig.1. Thermal expansion of CFRP

2.1.2 Ceramic material

There are some candidate materials to combine with the CFRP laminates. Though the glass ceramics such as Zerodure have good performance in terms of low CTE, they are relatively poor in machinability. SiC has the advantages of stiffness and strength, but the CTE is rather high. Cordierite has relatively low density, very low CTE at room temperature and excellent machinability. This ceramic material has many applications to industrial machine with a lot of precise holes for the fixtures. Thus, cordierite was finally selected as the ceramic material to combine with the CFRP structure in the hybrid composite structure. The density and the Young's modulus of this material was listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Properties of the Ceramics

Material Properties		
Density	g/cm ³	2.50
Young Modulus	GPa	137

The same procedure as in the CFRP was introduced to measure the CTE of the cordierite. Figure 2 shows the result. The CTE between 25° C and 80° C was -0.01ppm/k and 0.52 ppm/K between 80° C and 115° C which were in very good accordance with that of the CFRP laminates.

Fig.2. Thermal expansion of cordierite

2.1.3 Hybrid structure

In order to reduce the bi-metal effect due to the coupling the CFRP and the ceramic material, and to avoid the void contents in the adhesive between the parts, the cordierite top plate was directly attached to the CFRP lib structure as shown in Fig.3. Figure 4 shows the photo of the first demonstrator.

The size of the first structural demonstrator was 280 mm x 280 mm x 40 mm. The top and the bottom plates were made of cordierite whose thickness were about 2 mm. Inner ribs were made of CFRP laminates whose thickness were less than 1 mm.

The cordierite plates and the CFRP ribs were jointed using cyanate ester film adhesive in an oven. Before joining, the cordierite plates and the top and the bottom surface of the CFRP rib structure were ground as flat as 30 μm. This flatness was evaluated with the three dimensional measurement system by Mitsutoyo during the grinding procedure.

Fig. 3 Composition of the first demonstrator

Fig.4 The first demonstrator

2.1.4 Surface polishing

The top surface of the demonstrator was then polished using the grinder and the polisher. The target value of the flatness was $0.3\mu\text{m}$ in peak to valley, which corresponds to about a half of the wavelength. The surface flatness during the polishing was measured with an interferometer by Zygo.

2.2 The second demonstrator

2.2.1 CFRP material

In order to have better accordance of thermal expansion between the CFRP and the ceramic material, the thermal expansion of the CFRP was adjusted by adding a polymer sheet to the CFRP laminates. The revised CFRP pipe was fabricated and the CTE was measured.

The result is shown in Fig. 5 The CTE of the pipe was -0.03 ppm/K between 25°C and 80°C ,

which was quite close to that of the cordierite of -0.01 ppm/K .

Fig. 5 Thermal expansion of the revised CFRP

2.2.2 Ceramic material

The ceramic material used in the second demonstrator was the same as in the first one.

2.2.3 Hybrid structure

By combining the CFRP material which has lower CTE and the ceramic material, the second demonstrator shown in Fig. 6 was fabricated. The shape of the top plate was rectangular. Four skeleton structures of cordierite were added to increase the stiffness of the hybrid structure.

Fig. 6 Composition of the second demonstrator

Fig.7 The second demonstrator

The rib thickness of the cordierite skeleton structure was 3 mm to reduce weight for space applications. Figure 7 shows the photo of the second demonstrator.

2.2.4 Surface polishing

The top surface of the demonstrator was also polished using the grinder and the polisher as in 2.1.4. The target value of the flatness was also $0.3\mu\text{m}$ in peak to valley.

3 Evaluation of the demonstrator

3.1 The first demonstrator

3.1.1 Dimensional stability after adhesion

The changes in the flatness of the cordierite plate after the adhesion to the CFRP rib structure were measured using a non-contact three-dimension laser measurement system (Mitaka Kohki). Table 3 shows the result. A small change less than $22\mu\text{m}$ was observed both in the top plate and the bottom plate, which shows the good thermal stability of this hybrid structure.

Table 3 Surface accuracy (P-V value) of the first demonstrator after adhesion

Top surface	Bottom surface
$22\mu\text{m}$	$13\mu\text{m}$

In the first demonstrator, though the difference in the CTE is 0.33 ppm/K up to 80°C , the surface flatness of the hybrid structure after adhesion was within several dozens of microns,

which is good enough for the precise mechanical fittings.

3.1.2 Dimensional stability after polishing

The changes in the flatness of the cordierite plates after the polishing were also measured using a laser interferometer (Zygo). The results are shown in Fig. 8 and Table 4. In the top surface, a very good flatness of $0.1\mu\text{m}$ in RMS was observed. No quilting pattern was shown in Fig.8, which shows that the thickness of 2 mm was good enough for the polishing.

Fig.8 Surface accuracy of the second demonstrator

Table 4 Surface accuracy (RMS value) of CFRP/Ceramic hybrid after polish

Top surface	Bottom surface
$0.066\mu\text{m}$	$0.726\mu\text{m}$

3.2 The second demonstrator

3.1.2 Dimensional stability after adhesion

The changes in the flatness of the cordierite plate after the adhesion to the CFRP rib structure were measured in the same way as the first demonstrator. Table 5 shows the result after the adhesion. A good flatness was also confirmed in the second demonstrator.

Table 5 Surface accuracy (P-V value) of the second demonstrator after adhesion

Top surface	Bottom surface
23 μ m	40 μ m

3.2.2 Dimensional stability after polishing

Figure 9 shows the changes in the flatness of the cordierite plates after the polishing. By reducing the difference in CTE between CFRP rib structure and the cordierite plates, the flatness of the top plate was much improved to be 0.031 micron, which can be applied to an optical reflector.

Fig.9 Surface accuracy of the second demonstrator

4 Conclusions

A new lightweight hybrid composite structure for space optics was designed and a structural demonstrator was successfully fabricated. The average material density of the hybrid structure is about 2/3 of that of monolithic ceramic material. In addition, taking the limit to the machinable thickness of the ceramic material into account, the weight reduction of the whole structure is more than 50 %. The structure with the surface flatness of sub-micron level is not only thermally stable in

dimension but also easy to machine for making holes and interfaces.

The demonstrators show the very good feasibility for the optical parts such as mirrors and focal planes.

References

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